

Alkali Metal Complexes. Binuclear Alkali Metal Complexes with Magnesium(II) and Zinc(II) Acetylacetonates

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Heterobinuclear alkali metal complexes have been synthesised by treating metal chelates of magnesium and zinc acetylacetonates with alkali metal salts of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol and 8-hydroxyquinoline in ethanol/benzene-ethanol mixture. The general formula of the complex has been established as $[M_a(acac)_2 M_b L]$, where M_a = magnesium or zinc, acac = acetylacetonate, and $M_b L$ = Li, Na and K salt of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol and 8-hydroxyquinoline. The infrared stretching bands of C=O in adducts reveal the presence of bridged and unbridged oxygen atoms, and the bridging has been assigned to be due to attachment of oxygen atoms with alkali metal ions.

IN recent years the formation of oxygen bridged complexes containing two different ligands has been of interest to coordination chemists. The formation of oxygen bridged binuclear complexes from metal salicylaldimine has been well established by Gruber *et al.*¹

In the present work, binuclear complexes of magnesium and zinc acetylacetonates with alkali metal salts of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol and 8-hydroxyquinoline have been synthesised and the structures investigated with particular regard to their coordination sites.

Results and Discussion

Our usual method of preparation was to make a concentrated solution of the alkali metal salts in ethanol/ethanol-benzene mixture and add to it twice the molar quantity of the second ligand, magnesium- or zinc-acetylacetonate. The mixture was refluxed for 3 to 4 h with constant stirring. Then it was filtered while hot and washed with hot ethanol/ethanol-benzene mixture and dried in an oven at 90°. Analytical data showed that one molecule of alkali metal salts, $M_b L$, combined with one molecule of $M_a(acac)_2$ and the general formula of the adduct has been established as $[M_a(acac)_2 M_b L]$, where M_a = magnesium or zinc; L = Li, Na or K salt of deprotonated 1-nitroso-2-naphthol and 8-hydroxyquinoline.

All the complexes are quite stable in dry air and were kept in a desiccator over solid anhydrous calcium chloride. The complexes are slightly soluble in ethanol/ethanol-benzene mixture, but are insoluble in other non-polar solvents. The transition and decomposition temperatures of the complexes are much higher than that of the ligands, showing their greater stability. The analyses and

physical properties of these complexes are given in Table 1.

The infrared spectra (nujol) of all the compounds have been measured in the region 4000-200 cm^{-1} . The C=O absorption bands are given in Table 2. Significant differences were observed in the infrared spectrum of the parent ligand, Mg- or Zn-acetylacetonates before and after the formation of binuclear complexes.

It has been observed² that when transition metal acetylacetonate complex is a monomer, the C=O stretching frequency ranges between 1580 to 1555 cm^{-1} . In case of nickel acetylacetonate, which is a trimer, this C=O frequency splits into two, one is at 1595 cm^{-1} and the other at 1560 cm^{-1} . Looking into the crystal structure of $[\text{Ni}(\text{acac})_2]_3$, it has been observed that half the oxygen atoms are bridged oxygens, *i.e.* one oxygen attached to two Ni^{2+} . The other six oxygen atoms are only attached to one Ni^{2+} . These latter six C=O seem to be normal ones, and fall in the range of monomers (1588-1555 cm^{-1}). Owing to bridging character of the former six oxygens or when one oxygen is donating electrons to two Ni^{2+} , the C=O frequency goes up, and shows at 1595 cm^{-1} . This shift is expected due to the maintenance of a ring current arising from electron delocalisation in the chelate ring. The Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} acetylacetonates are also dimers and in these, two C=O frequencies are reported³, one normal at 1560 and 1565 cm^{-1} , and the other, the bridged ones at 1588 and 1605 cm^{-1} , respectively.

It can thus be generalised that in metal acetylacetonates when they are monomers, the C=O frequency is below 1580 cm^{-1} whereas, when it is a polymer, with oxygen bridges, the C=O frequency splits into two, one above 1580 cm^{-1} (due to bridging) and the other normal below 1580 cm^{-1} .

TABLE 1

Compd.	Colour	Decomposition temperature °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
			C	H	N	Mg/Zn	M*
Mg(acac) ₂ ≡ X	White	191					
LiIN2N.X	Greenish brown	222-224	58.40 (59.85)	5.20 (4.98)	3.12 (3.49)	5.73 (5.98)	—
NaIN2N.X	Yellowish brown	230-233	56.10 (57.55)	4.91 (4.79)	3.24 (3.35)	5.31 (5.75)	5.41 (5.51)
KIN2N.X	Brown	219-222	55.02 (55.42)	5.10 (5.36)	3.21 (3.46)	5.14 (5.54)	8.44 (9.00)
Li8HQ.X	Light yellow	204-206	60.43 (61.12)	5.91 (5.36)	3.32 (3.75)	6.12 (6.43)	—
Na8HQ.X	Light yellow	200-203	57.32 (58.61)	5.41 (5.14)	3.20 (3.60)	5.92 (6.18)	5.82 (5.91)
K8HQ.X	Light yellow	198-200	55.16 (56.29)	4.30 (4.93)	3.19 (3.46)	5.76 (5.92)	9.42 (9.62)
Zn(acac) ₂ ≡ Y	White	162					
LiIN2N.Y	Greenish brown	217	53.62 (54.27)	4.92 (4.52)	2.80 (3.16)	14.73 (14.77)	—
NaIN2N.Y	Light greenish brown	215-219	51.62 (52.14)	4.20 (4.36)	2.62 (3.05)	14.11 (14.26)	4.70 (5.01)
KIN2N.Y	Greenish brown	206-209	49.30 (59.59)	4.76 (4.20)	2.41 (2.95)	13.43 (13.77)	7.83 (8.22)
Li8HQ.Y	Light yellow	198-200	54.12 (55.02)	5.36 (4.82)	2.90 (3.37)	15.52 (15.77)	—
Na8HQ.Y	Light yellow	191-194	51.96 (52.97)	4.92 (4.64)	3.16 (3.25)	14.94 (15.19)	5.23 (5.34)
K8HQ.Y	yellow	206	50.73 (51.08)	4.93 (4.48)	2.70 (3.13)	14.41 (14.64)	8.32 (8.74)

* M = Li, Na or K.

 TABLE 2—POSITION OF C=O BAND (cm⁻¹) IN VARIOUS ALKALI METAL BINUCLEAR COMPLEX COMPOUNDS WITH Mg(acac)₂ AND Zn(acac)₂

Compd.	$\nu_{C=O}$	+ $\nu_{C=O}$
Mg(acac) ₂ ≡ X	1608	
LiIN2N.X	1614	1605
NaIN2N.X	1614	1580
KIN2N.X	1605	1595
Li8HQ.X	1613	1605
Na8HQ.X	1608	1582
K8HQ.X	1620sh	1610
Zn(acac) ₂ ≡ Y	1588	
LiIN2N.Y	1615	1590
NaIN2N.Y	1614	1590
KIN2N.Y	1614	1585
Li8HQ.Y	1614	1587
Na8HQ.Y	1595	1585
K8HQ.Y	1595	1580

An examination of the C=O bands of ligands Mg(acac)₂ and Zn(acac)₂, as well as, the binuclear complexes of alkali metal salts with these metal chelates, reveals the presence of both bridged and unbridged oxygen atoms in these binuclear complexes. The C=O band in the ligand Mg(acac)₂ at 1608 cm⁻¹ invariably splits into two in its alkali metal complexes, one at the normal position ~1608 cm⁻¹ and the other at 1614-1620 cm⁻¹ slightly higher than the normal. The same observations are made also in case of Zn(acac)₂-alkali metal complexes. The normal C=O vibrations at 1588 cm⁻¹ in the ligand, Zn(acac)₂, is also present in its alkali metal complexes. Besides, there is another at higher region, between 1595 and 1614 cm⁻¹.

The presence of atleast one of the band in the vicinity of 1580-1600 cm⁻¹, the normal range of C=O stretching frequency in the complexes, shows the existence of unbridged oxygen whereas, the presence of bands shifted to higher frequency compared to those of ligand C=O stretching frequency bands, suggests the bridging of some of the oxygen atoms. These oxygens are probably bridged due to donation of lone pair of electrons to the alkali metals.

In all the complexes, the higher shift of C=O stretching frequency shows the increased bond order between the carbon and oxygen atoms as a result of coordination of the oxygen atom to the alkali metals. This suggests an increased aromaticity of the heterocyclic ring containing the Mg or Zn atoms due to the alkali metal complex formation, and that in turn enforces greater stability, as seen by the higher decomposition temperatures, compared to that of the ligands.

The infrared spectral observations regarding the probable presence of unbridged oxygen atoms in the complexes, is well in agreement with 1 : 1 stoichiometry of the complexes derived from the analytical data. The small shift of C=O frequency in the binuclear alkali metal complexes shows the bonding between the alkali metals and the oxygen atoms to be rather weak.

Magnesium- and zinc-acetylacetonates are double faced bidentate ligands, still they coordinate with only one molecule of alkali metal salts of organic

acids. It is quite likely that the steric effect of the ligands prevented addition of two molecules of alkali metal salts. Though all the four oxygen atoms around Mg/Zn ion of the acetylacetonates are equivalent, it is presumed that after the addition of one molecule of alkali metal salt, due to conjugated system present in the acetylacetonates, the donor properties of other two oxygen atoms decreased, resulting in the attachment of only one molecule of alkali metal salt.

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